

MISSING LETTER APPLICATION STRENGTHENING VOCABULARY FOR JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT.

The purpose of this study is to determine whether missing letter applications can improve students' vocabulary in the eighth grade at SMP Muhammadiyah 3 Bontoala during the 2019/2020 academic year. The subjects were eighth-grade students. The researcher collects data using pre-test, treatment, and post-test methods. The test consisted of 20 questions given in the pre-test during the first meeting, and the post-test included 20 questions during the last meeting. This is pre-experimental research. It is possible to conclude that using the missing letter application improves students' vocabulary, especially for nouns. The results revealed that the t-test was higher than the t-table ($7.881 > 2.093$). So, H1 (alternative Hypothesis) was accepted, but H0 (Null Hypothesis) was rejected. The mean post-test score is 87.25 than pre-test which is 73.50. Thus, there was a big improvement.

Keywords: Missing letter application, strengthening students' vocabulary

INTRODUCTION

The language contains some aspects, such as grammar and vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the most crucial language components to teach youngsters. Recognizing enough vocabulary helps pupils communicate and understand English easily, as vocabulary is at the basis of the language. acquiring a language involves acquiring vocabulary. It is fundamental to communication and is also vital in the acquisition process (Krashen, 1981: 12). It means that mastering a language requires memorizing its vocabulary. It is critical to present it to youngsters as a foundational step to help them grasp utterances and prepare them to learn English at the next level. Vocabulary mastery has an important function in achieving four language skills. Teachers can use a variety of approaches to increase vocabulary mastery. They are expanding their vocabulary by teaching letter idioms, phrases, sentences, clauses, songs, quizzes, puzzles, reading, writing passages, and activities. Games are considered one of the most effective strategies for teaching vocabulary.

There are numerous reasons why games are so useful in the language-learning classroom. According to Mc. Cullum and George in Maslaeni (1980), games can naturally increase student attention. A properly introduced game can be one of the most effective motivators. According to Carrier (1980), adding games in language classes can help sustain enthusiasm, break up long formal teaching units, and refresh students' energy before moving on to more formal learning. Missing Letters is a comparable game that can be used well for vocabulary instruction. Shinta (2012) suggests that using Missing Letters in learning and teaching is beneficial for three reasons: (1) it is simple to practice, (2) it aligns with students' vocabulary acquisition, and (3) it is easily customizable. Missing letter application is one of the mobile phone applications that kids or young learners can download. It is created for young minds and small fingers, and the gameplay is easy, with voice coaching. Missing Letter is a letter recognition game that allows pupils to identify which letter is missing from each word. The objective of this research is to know Whether or not missing letter applications improve the student's English vocabulary. Some researchers have conducted studies that focus on the Missing Letter Application. Some study findings are closely related to this research. Rello et al. (2014) introduce Dyslexia, a game application with word workouts for dyslexic children. They are designing the game's content using linguistic and educational criteria, as well as corpus analysis. The key contributions are the design of activities based on the analysis of errors written by dyslexics, as well as the presentation of Spanish reinforcement exercises as a computer game. The game is available for free on both iOS and Android. In her thesis, Pertiwi (2016) explores if playing missing letters can successfully boost vocabulary. Her has a particular technique for deaf children that provides a more effective way to improve English vocabulary.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this study is an experiment. This experimental inquiry can be understood as a method of investigation utilized to determine the influence of one treatment on others in a control condition. In this study, the researchers used a pre-experimental approach with a single class and provided a pre-test, treatment, and post-test design. This study's population consisted of eighth-grade students from SMP Muhammadiyah 3 Bontoala during the academic year 20019/2020. The total population was 25 students. The researcher selected the research sample and respondent. The sample size was 20 students in eighth grade. The researcher selected this class using the cluster random sampling technique. This research has two variables: a. Missing letter application was employed as an independent variable to enhance pupils' vocabulary development. Missing Letter application is a mobile phone game that helps keep pupils entertained and interested. b. The dependent variable was to expand the student's vocabulary, and evaluate, and utilize knowledge based on graphics and sounds that could be obtained through a mobile phone application. In the test, the researcher encourages students to download the Missing Letter program beforehand and then construct pairs of vocabulary

up to 20, so that researchers can analyse students' success in the classroom. The researcher handed the students paper, and the students then wrote down the missing letter on the paper. The test was administered before, during, and after treatment. Classes will begin with a pre-test before treatment. The pre-test is designed to assess the student's vocabulary. The post-test is used to determine whether or not the student's vocabulary has improved after being treated with the Missing Letter Application. In this study, data was collected using a test instrument with pre-test, treatment, and post-test. The writer used the following steps when gathering data: 1. Before treatment, the writer administered a pre-test to the students.

2. After administering the pre-test, the writer provided treatment in four meetings. It was like a teaching and learning process with the Missing Letter Application.

3. Following treatment, the writer administered a post-test to pupils using different sentences from the pre-test to assess their progress in teaching and learning.

4. Students' pre-and post-test scores were tabulated and analyzed using a method.

The data for the analysis was acquired using pre-test and post-test procedures. The researcher used the following formula:

1. Classifying students' vocabulary exam scores using the scale below:

The score of students' vocabulary test

Score	Classification	Criteria
96 - 100	Excellent	One - None of one error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
86 – 95	Very Good	Two error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
76 – 85	Good	Three error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
66 – 75	Fairly Good	Four error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
56 – 65	Fairly	Five error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
36 – 55	Poor	Five error of remember and memorized the vocabulary
0 – 35	Very Poor	Seven – none of wrong remember and memorized the vocabulary

(Depdikbud, 2006)

2. Scoring the students' correct answer pre-test and post-test

$$Score = \frac{\text{students' scores}}{\text{Total number of score}} \times 100$$

(Arikunto, 2010)

3. Calculating the mean score of the students

$$X = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where: X = the mean score

$\sum X$ = the students' total score.

N = the number of the students

(Gay LR, 2012)

4. To find the students' improvement the formula as follows:

$$\% = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{x_1} \times 100$$

Where:

% = the students' improving

X1 = the mean score of post-test

X2 = the mean score of pre-test

(Gay, 2012)

5. Computing the frequency and the percentage of the students' score

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

P = Percentage

F = Frequency

N = the total number of students

(Gay, 2012)

1. Find out the students' standard deviation by using SPSS (Statistical product and service solution)
2. Finding out the significant difference between the score of the pre-test and post-test by using
3. The criteria for the hypothesis testing also using SPSS.

Table 3.4 Hypothesis Testing

Comparison	Hypothesis	
	H0	H1
t-test < t-table	Accepted	Rejected
t-test > t-table	Rejected	Accepted

(Gay, 2012)

FINDINGS

The research findings described the outcomes of the data analysis. The vocabulary test consisted of two parts: the pre-test and the post-test. A pre-test was administered to determine the students' vocabulary before the treatment, and a post-test was given to determine the development of students' vocabulary achievement following treatment. To collect data, the researcher administered a pre-test and a post-test, and the results showed that the post-test outperformed the pre-test, indicating that the media (missing letter application) worked.

Frequency of students' pre-test vocabulary test

No	Score	Category	Pre-test	
			Frequency	Percentage
1.	96-100	Excellent	0	0%
2.	86-95	Very good	1	5%
3.	76-85	Good	8	40%
4.	66-75	Fairly good	7	35%
5.	56-65	Fairly	1	5%
6.	36-55	Poor	3	15%
7.	0-35	Very poor	0	0%
TOTAL			20	100%

The table shows the rate, percentage, and frequency of pupils' test vocabulary scores on the pre-test. There were 20 students in the sample, and none of them were classified as excellent, 1 student (5%) as very good, 8 students (40%) as good, 7 students (35%) as fairly good, 1 student (5%) as fairly, and 3 students (15%) as very poor, with no student in the very poor category.

Frequency score of students’ post-test vocabulary test

No	Score	Category	Post-test	
			Frequency	Percentage
1.	96-100	Excellent	1	5%
2.	86-95	Very good	10	50%
3.	76-85	Good	7	35%
4.	66-75	Fairly good	2	10%
5.	56-65	Fairly	0	0%
6.	36-55	Poor	0	0%
7.	0-35	Very poor	0	0%
TOTAL			20	100%

The table shows the rate, percentage, and frequency of students' test vocabulary scores in the post-test. Then, in the post-test, one student (5%) was classified as excellent, ten students (50%) as very good, seven students (35%) as good, two students (10%) as fairly good, and no students were classified as fairly, poor, or extremely poor. It meant that the pupils' vocabulary score on the post-test was higher than the percentage on the pre-test.

The mean score and standard deviation of the students’ vocabulary

Indicator	Pre-Test	Post-Test	Improvement
Vocabulary Improvements	73.50	87.25	19.43%
Standard Deviation	13.387	6.781	

The table displayed the students' mean pre-test and post-test scores, as well as their vocabulary improvement. The mean score of students' vocabulary was around 73.05 and the post-test score was 87.25. It was provided that using missing letter application to improve students' vocabulary with an increase of 19.43% by the pre-test and post-test average score, where the post-test score was higher and had a significant increase in the pre-test mean score after treatment.

The improvement of the students’ vocabulary

The student score increased from the pre-test to the post-test. Scores were achieved after evaluating pupils' vocabulary exams following treatment. The mean value increased dramatically from 73.05 in the pre-test to 87.25 in the post-test. It demonstrated that employing the missing letter application to develop students' translations resulted in a 19.43% increase.

Based on the above discussion, it is possible to conclude that the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected, whereas the alternative hypothesis was accepted both before and after the usage of a missing letter application among eighth-grade students at SMP Muhammadiyah 3 Bontoala.

The discussion part of this research: The primary goal of this study was to determine whether missing letter application improves students' English vocabulary among eighth-grade students at SMP Muhammadiyah 3 Bontoala. To determine the purpose, the research employed the test as an instrument, with a pre-test, treatment, and post-test.

This study employed the Missing Letter application to boost students' English vocabulary because the application is interesting to learn, and all students enjoyed using the Missing Letter application in teaching and learning. They grow enthused about their studies and commit to memorizing some sentences from Indonesian to English. The Missing Letter Application was enjoyable, and it improved the pupils' motivation to study English. They actively participate in the learning process and ask questions about the Missing Letter Application. It can be used anywhere and is simple to implement in teaching. This is evident from the increase in student scores.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussion, it is possible to conclude that missing letter application, particularly for students' noun vocabulary, improved students' English vocabulary; as seen by the results, the t-test was higher than the t-table ($7.881 > 2.093$). So, H1 (alternative Hypothesis) was accepted, but H0 (Null Hypothesis) was rejected. Also, the post-test mean score is 87.25, which is greater than the pre-test mean score of 73.50. Thus, there was a considerable difference. Using the missing letter application, students

in the eighth grade at SMP Muhammadiyah 3 Bontoala improved their English vocabulary.

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